

HEPATITIS B DISEASE - CAUSES, SYMPTOMS, COMPLICATIONS, TREATMENT, PREVENTION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6230484>

Yuldasheva Nargiza

Toxtamatova Dilorom

*Teachers of the Technical College of Public Health
named after Abu Ali ibn Sino*

Abstract: *Hepatitis B is an anthroponotic viral disease. The causative agent with significant hepatotoxic properties is caused by the hepatitis B virus (HBV), which belongs to the family of hepatadnaviruses. The virus is highly resistant to various physical and chemical factors.*

Key words: *hepatitis, virus, infection, vaccine, (HBV),*

The disease can only be transmitted through contact with the patient's biological materials. In most cases, the infection goes unnoticed by the patient, so the disease is detected by laboratory tests or when specific symptoms appear. Patients treated in a timely manner will recover completely and have a stable immunity to the disease.

Hepatitis B is a viral disease in which the virus begins to affect vital organs when it enters the body. The disease causes the most damage to the liver, which occurs at the microcellular level. The disease may be asymptomatic or present with clear symptoms. In the chronic stage, this viral infection often leads to the development of liver cirrhosis and cancer.

The probability of disease transition from acute to chronic can vary depending on certain characteristics of the organism:

In newborns - 90% of cases;

In young people with normal immunity - 1% of cases;

In older people - in 10% of cases.

People who are vaccinated develop immunity to this disease:

After the first vaccination - 50%;

After the second vaccination - 75%;

After the third vaccination - 100%.

Indications for the diagnosis of chronic forms of the disease in children:

In children aged 1-5 years - 25-50% of cases;

In 90% of newborns infected at birth.

People who are vaccinated develop immunity to this disease:

Group B hepatitis is classified as follows:

At lightning speed. Patients experience brain swelling within a few hours and are more likely to fall into a coma. In many cases, the patient's life ends tragically in the

short term as the disease progresses to the clinical stage. This form of the disease is very rare (less than 1%).

Sharp. In the acute form of hepatitis B, the patient has several stages of the disease. Initially, the main symptoms appear, and then the skin turns yellow. The final stage of the pathology is characterized by liver failure.

Chronic. The disease becomes chronic 1-6 months after infection. This is the incubation period of the virus for several months, after which specific symptoms and signs begin to appear.

Once the virus has entered the patient's body, the incubation period for hepatitis begins. It lasts from 30 to 180 days, with an average of 75 days.

Acute hepatitis can be:

Sensitivity phase;

Long-term illness;

Recidivism;

In rare cases - coma.

If hepatitis B is diagnosed late or not treated in time, it can increase the risk of developing liver cirrhosis or hepatocellular cancer.

This category of patients may experience other serious consequences of the disease:

Myocarditis (inflammation of the heart muscle);

Arthritis, osteoarthritis and other joint diseases;

Stroke, kidney disease and others.

The risk of death from these complications is significantly increased.

At the state level, the list of people in need of compulsory vaccination against hepatitis B has been approved:

Pupils and students of the school;

Kindergarten students;

Healthcare professionals who can make contact with patients' biological materials;

Patients in need of hemodialysis;

Patients in need of intravenous injection;

Persons serving sentences in prisons;

Family members and friends of a patient suffering from chronic hepatitis;

Those who have irregular sex;

Tourists planning trips to settlements where an epidemic of this disease has been recorded.

REFERENCES:

1. M.F.Ziyayeva. Z.O.Rizayeva. "Bolalarda hamshiralik parvarishi". Toshkent, "Fan va texnologiya" 2012 yil.
2. X.N Fayziyev. « Сестринский уход за детьми » Toshkent, «Ilm ziyo» nashriyoti, 2008 yil

3. K.S Inomov. «Pediatriyada hamshiralik ishi» Toshkent, 2007 yil
4. www.ziyonet.uz
5. <https://mymedic.uz/>